

Visual practices for the representation of sound in silent cartoons: character animation series in the USA in the 1920s

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Abstract

With the growth of industrialization and animation studios in the 1920s, silent North American cartoons developed their own visual aesthetics through which they created sound suggestions. Through the analysis of films of the time, this study seeks to identify the practices used in the silent period, such as pantomime, intertitles, and close-up on the sound source, as well as the exclusive devices of the animation technique, such as dialogue balloons and animation of texts and symbols, with the purpose of contributing to other studies that can identify the extinction or adaptation of these devices following the advent of sound and its legacy in the current animated language.

Keywords: Silent cinema, animation, sound, cartoon, animated film, Disney animation

Introduction

During the 1920s, we observed a notable growth in the North American animated film industry. Production in massive quantities has resulted in the standardization of visual and narrative codes, among which comedy has emerged as the main genre of animation in its silent phase (Crafton, 1993). The spot-gag structure is a common feature of most animated films produced in that decade. The possibilities of image manipulation generated comical effects that brought the audience a new visual vocabulary, which animated cinema came to explore and develop (Wells, 1998). In particular, cartoon makes use of resources typical of graphic

narrative, which explores its two-dimensional space in a surrealist way, defying perspective or plausibility (Klein, 1993).

Comic strips had been helping to create a vocabulary for animated films since the 1910s. Winsor McCay translated his style from comics to cartoons, prioritizing narrative structure and bringing the notion of personality to an animated character (Wells, 1998).

Adaptations of comic strips became a trend from 1913 onwards, but in the following decade the most consolidated format was the character series specially created for the big screen, such as Felix the Cat, Koko the Clown and Oswald the Lucky Rabbit.

The legacy of the comic form, as well as several visual elements and sound cues typical of comics, would remain present in animated cinema, especially during the silent period. Solutions such as the animation of texts and symbols not only replaced the traditional features of live action cinema, such as intertitles and close-ups, but also allowed new relationships within the animated film, as it was possible to create movements with these elements. Metamorphosis, for example, a device that Wells highlights as being “unique to the animated form” (1998:69), was applied to a word to transform it into an object integral to the diegesis. The word not only represents its semantic content but also becomes a visual element, making use of its own graphic characteristics to “materialize” in a way that directly interferes with the narrative. As Chion points out, the silent cartoon “had the luxury of representing sounds visually, using the same codes as comic books” (2009, p.39).

In the silent period, it was already well known that the addition of music and sound effects to accompany the film indicated the reading of the image, established atmosphere, rhythm and in the case of comedic films, highlighted gags. Some directors even prepared song recommendations or a score composed specifically to be performed live (Manzano, 2003). Sound accompaniment manuals at the time indicated the use of themes and sounds for each type of film. For Lang and West, a good accompanist should have a rich repertoire, great ability to improvise, in addition to being up to date with phonographic releases to attract the public to their movie theater (Goldmark & Taylor, 2002). Composer Carl Stalling - who worked with Walt Disney in the 1920s and Warner Bros. in the 1930s - began his career as an accompanist, which certainly influenced his style later in his work with musical scores (Curtis, 1992). On the other hand, we must consider researcher Rick Altman's insistent claim that not all projection

rooms had accompanists for the live performance (Szaloky, 2002), just as there was no control over what this accompaniment would be like, since this basically depended on the structure of each room¹. Thus, it was necessary for silent cinema to develop a capacity for visual sound suggestion, to the point of making the film a complete work regardless of whether there was sound accompaniment. According to Manzano:

[E]ven great directors were concerned that the film spoke for itself, without depending on the score. The fact is that this happened, since even today many films, when watched and appreciated without their "original" accompaniment, they still preserve their qualities and characteristics that have kept them interesting over time. (2003, p.31)

Using a set of films by Disney and Otto Messmer/Pat Sullivan, we will reflect on how visual solutions are used to represent sounds in these cartoons.

Bibliographical review

Most studies on sound in silent cinema focus on sound accompaniment, especially music. Little is said about the "internal sound" of the films, or the visual practices that compensate for the absence of a synchronized soundtrack.

We find in the article by Melinda Szaloky (2002) a theoretical reflection with a case study, listing some of the exclusive devices of the silent period, such as intertitles and explanatory plans. The author draws attention to "an acoustic dimension of the silent cinema that has been insufficiently recognized, one that does not originate from extrafilmic sound effects but, instead, issues from the images themselves." (Szaloky, 2002, p. 110)

Luiz Adelmo Manzano (2003) presents the main practices of sound representation, bringing Musterberg's perceptions in the first theoretical reflections on cinema and Chion's analysis of procedures for expressing sounds in silent cinema, as for example in Eisenstein's *The Strike* (1925), where the use of a close-up image of a power plant siren appears as an insert shot periodically, bringing unity and continuity to the sequence, becoming a visual refrain. Manzano also presents Marcel Martin's systematization with emphasis on the "sound chaos"

¹There is a great deal of discussion about sound accompaniment practices during silent cinema. Altman counters the majority argument that "cinema was never silent", arguing with the distinct phases of silent cinema and scopes of projection rooms (Altman, 1994).

effect produced by the rapid editing. For Manzano, the broad grammar of silent cinema is developed based on editing, both in terms of the composition of each shot and the edited sequence. We also find in this text the mention of live-action films that even use the animation technique in the intertitle texts to express the idea of sounds, as in *Metropolis* (1927) or with the use of trickery, as in *The Woman in the Moon* (1929), both by Fritz Lang.

However, no study was found covering the use of these and other devices specifically in silent animated short films, as well as practices that can only be found with the animation technique.

Regarding animated cinema, we find in the works of Maltin (1987) and Crafton (1982) a historical overview of the main developments in the industry over the decades, with emphasis on the technical and aesthetic innovations of the "golden age" of animation studios. Merrit and Kaufman (1993) provide an in-depth behind-the-scenes approach to the initial period of Walt Disney's studio. Paul Wells (1998) reflects on the language specificities of the animation technique with several case studies. Despite having been rare until a certain period, sound studies in animation have increased significantly since the 2000s, according to the analysis by Taberham (2018).

However, when we specifically analyze the period of silent cinema in Sound Studies, mention of animated films is rare, just as little is said in Animation Studies about sound representation practices. It was with the intention of helping to fill one of these "blind spots" that one of the authors developed in 2009 a master's research (published only in Portuguese) to collect information and observations about the transition between the silent and sound period of the animation film industry.

This text is a continuation of the studies that were previously part of the master's thesis, with an update of its references, translation into English and review of the concepts presented.

Method

This study presents how some cartoons (in this case, North American character series from the 1920s), in addition to editing, make use of the animation technique itself to suggest sounds through images.

Silent films were selected from the animated series Felix the Cat (until 1928), Alice Comedies, Oswald the Lucky Rabbit (only those produced by Walt Disney) and the first 3 films in the Mickey Mouse series. These series are some of the most popular in the so-called studio period of the 1920s (Crafton, 1993) and are commonly found in public archives today, even though not all films produced are available. They are also the works that have been analyzed the most by animation film theorists such as Crafton and Merrit and Kaufman, and where the main methods of systematizing film production were observed. The Alice and Oswald series contain Disney's works that preceded Mickey Mouse, famous for having incorporated sound from the third film in the series (and first to be released), *Steamboat Willie*, in 1928. In the case of Felix, the selected films were produced between 1925 and 1928, for comparison purposes to Disney films.

It is worth mentioning that the versions found may have undergone changes in relation to their original format. For the Alice, Oswald and Mickey series, most of the films were obtained from the *Disney Treasures* collection, released commercially on DVD in 2007. The remaining films were accessed from public archives on the Internet, on YouTube and Archive.org.

Finally, as is to be expected, all silent films currently available contain a soundtrack produced especially to accompany the works. On the *Disney Treasures* DVD, Robert Israel composed the music to be released in 5.1. As we have previously highlighted the importance of adding sound, with the understanding that watching a film with or without the soundtrack are different experiences. However, to avoid the influencing effect of sound stimuli and to observe how much the narratives of these films are understandable by themselves with images only, we chose to analyze the films by watching them in silence.

Results

Observing the practices used to visually suggest sounds in the films studied, we can classify them into the following groups:

- a) Rhythmic establishing shot
- b) Pantomime
- c) Animation of texts and symbols

d) Close-up on the sound source

e) Concert and dance

For this study, it was decided not to separate the sounds in the "classic" way of cinema (dialogues, music and noises), considering that there is no soundtrack that contains these elements, but rather, visual representations that can be used to transmit more than one type of sound.

Discussion

Let us look at each characteristic listed above on a case-by-case basis:

a) Rhythmic establishing shot

In addition to the traditional functions of an establishing shot, it is also used to propose a musical rhythm through the cycle animation of the elements in the scene. This beat, which can indicate a character's emotional state, may serve as a rhythmic basis for musical accompaniment.

In *Plane Crazy* (1928), the film's first scene consists of a long shot of an airplane building on a farm. Several characters are working at a steady pace: the pig hammers a nail, the dog saws a board, the duck and another pig assemble the plane. In this shot, a beat can be visually identified that may serve as a reference for the accompaniment music at the beginning of the film.

Plane Crazy (1928)

In *Gallop in' Gaucho* (1928), the establishing shot has Mickey riding an ostrich, which runs at a steady pace, also establishing a common beat.

The Gallop in ' Gaucho (1928)

In Disney's Oswald series films, the establishing shot is also often used with the same function. It is not always the first shot of the film, but it appears right at the beginning, most of the time presenting a scene in a cycle, where the setting and action offer the viewer important information about the location and characters, so that the conflict is later presented, in addition to establishing the musical rhythm that may guide the accompaniment musician.

b) Pantomime

Pantomime is a device widely used during the silent film era to represent dialogue visually. In silent cartoon series, communication between characters is most often conducted entirely with gestures to avoid the use of intertitles or dialogue balloons.

Felix the Cat frequently uses pantomime to communicate.

Comicalamities (1928)

In Disney's *Oswald*, the characters open their mouths during gestures, even though no subtitles or intertitles are displayed, which would be unnecessary, as the action already replaces any text.

In *Plane Crazy* (1928), there is a striking use of mime in the scene in which Mickey invites Minnie to board the plane: Mickey points to Minnie and makes a gesture of flying. In the post-sound version released, Minnie's voice was placed over her "Who, me?" gesture, even though it ends up being redundant in terms of the action.

Plane Crazy (1928)

c) Animation of texts and symbols

The use of texts and symbols to represent sounds was already a common resource in comic strips at the time and easily adapted for cartoons, where the possibility of animating the letters and working on them over time could also be added.

The most common examples of texts and symbols found in the films studied are:

- Laughter ("Ha Ha", "He He")

In *Plane Crazy* (1928), Mickey makes fun of Minnie and the words "Ha Ha" appear over him, as in comics, but animated, making it possible to convey the rhythm and duration of the laugh.

Plane Crazy (1928)

- Slam / Stroke (“Crash”, “Bang”, “Pow”, etc.)

In *Plane Crazy*, the plane crashing to a tree is accompanied by the words “Crash” and “Bang”.

Plane Crazy (1928)

Felix the Cat - Astronomous (1927)

In Disney's *Oswald*, offscreen actions are explored using the animation of words and symbols representing a fight or accident coming from somewhere behind an object or outside the viewer's perspective.

Fight inside the cave in *Tall Timber (1928)*

- Shouts (“Help”, “Ouch”, “Wow” etc.)

The animation of letters is one of the most used devices to convey intensity to a given action: a tremor could punctuate a harsh scream; The variation in size of the letters also indicates the intensity of the sound.

Felix in Fairyland (1923)

The Gallopin' Gaucho (1928)

In the episode *Oh, Teacher*, from *Oswald the Lucky Rabbit* (1927), we find a unique use of subtitles, which becomes part of the action and constitutes a gag. In this example, we can observe some particularities of the animation: the possibility of indicating the “path” of the sound: the word is emitted from the character's mouth and reaches the ear (or close) of another character. In the scene in question, this particularly interesting resource is applied, that of manipulating the word in space and time, visually representing physical properties of the sound, such as: 1) amplitude: through the size and stylization of the font, which can indicate the intensity of the sound ; 2) projection in space and time: through the displacement of the word in determined positions and speeds; 3) timbre: through the deformation of the source, which can indicate a vibration or another characteristic of the sound.

We also observe the possibility of a transmutation of the word into an object integral to the diegesis. The word not only represents its semantic content, but also becomes a visual element, making use of its own graphic characteristics to “materialize” in a way that directly interferes with the narrative. This device is quite common in *Felix the Cat* with the famous question mark that turns into a hook (or any other useful object) (Telotte, 2011).

In this scene, the word "Help" runs to Oswald, but because he is distracted, it has to kick him to get him to take action. Afterwards, he uses it as a horse to get to the rabbit who is in danger.

Oswald the Lucky Rabbit - Oh, Teacher (1927): subtitles are a part of the action, creating a gag: The word “Help” comes out of the rabbit’s mouth and floats to Oswald, who apparently doesn’t notice it. The word kicks the character and points to where help is needed. Oswald turns the word into a “horse”, mounts it and reaches the rabbit.

In Disney's *Oswald*, there are several examples of spoken words participating in the action. Another gag with the word "Help" punching him is used in *All Wet* (1927). The same film ends with Oswald receiving a kick from the word "Smack" of a kiss that the bunny gives him as thanks, preceding the "happy ending" wrap with the couple's passionate kiss.

The word "Whoa" stops the horse in *The Fox Chase* (1928)

- Whistle / Horn / Mechanical sounds (“Honk”, “Toot”, “Click”, “Dong”)

Objects that play a key role in a scene are often accompanied by its associated sound represented visually by its onomatopoeia word.

Felix Finds Out (1924)

In *Rival Romeos* (1927), the same trajectory of the word “Help” in *Oh Teacher* is observed, now with the onomatopoeia "Honk": the visual sound comes from inside the rival dog’s horn, reaches Oswald, tries to punch him in the face, but Oswald reacts and bursts it with a slap.

Rival Romeos (1927)

In Disney's *Oswald*, mechanical equipment is often accompanied by the onomatopoeia associated with its sound.

The Mechanical Cow (1927)

- Kiss (“Smack” or “Kiss”)

The kiss sound is represented by the word “smack” or “kiss”. Depending on the font size and length of the text, the word can also indicate the intensity and duration of the kiss.

Felix Bursts a Bubble (1926)

Kiss is "thrown" in *Oswald – Oh, What a Knight (1927)*

- Animal sounds (“Bow ow”, “Quacks”, “Rrrr”)

Animal sounds are also represented by their corresponding onomatopoeia.

In a scene from *All Wet* (1927), there is a "Food is Fun" gag type (Wright, 2012), in which a character (ironically an anthropomorphized dog) "fights" with his food. When trying to bite the hot dog twice, the sausage barks, alluding to the name of the food (which in Wright's classification, would also fit as a "multiple reference" gag). On the third attempt, it emits screams of pain (conveyed by the words "Ouch", "Eee", "Stop", as well as dashes and dots symbols), until the character becomes sensitized, pets the sausage and lets it go (signaling with pantomime), giving it a sad and embarrassed goodbye.

Sausage "barks" in *Oswald - All Wet* (1927)

In *Alice Gets Stung* (1925), there is a musical scene, with the use of a gag type that will be recycled and adapted in the sound era *Mickey Mouse* films: the instrumentation of animals, in which they are arranged as part of a drum kit or an orchestra. In the silent period, animal sounds are represented by texts that indicate the type of animal noise.

Animal drum kit in *Alice Gets Stung* (1925)

– Snoring / Sleeping / Smell ("Zzzz", "Sniff")

To represent a sleeping character, the animation of the letter "Z" is used, repeated several times.

Rabbits sleep in the den in *Alice Gets Stung* (1925)

Felix smells a fish in *Felix Gets the Can* (1924)

- Metaphors: musical notes, hearts, stars, punctuation and vibration strokes

The use of metaphorical drawings representing musical notes (mostly eighth notes) was already common in comic strips and was adopted by cartoons from the silent period until the beginning of the sound period.

Notes can also represent the “path” of sound: they come from an instrument or a singer’s mouth and arrive close to the characters’ ears, representing the “hearing” of characters.

Felix plays under a window in
Arabiantics (1928)

Notes "enter" through the
window

Characters dance to the music

Gags about notes are common, as for example in Oswald's serenade in *Rival Romeos*, in which at a certain point two notes fight each other, exchanging punches until they disappear.

Rival Romeos (1927)

In *Astronomeous (1927)*, there are lines indicating the vibration of the radio, the source of the sound that the cats are listening to.

Astronomeous (1927)

Question marks and exclamation marks were already common in comic strips, also used in silent films to indicate the character's state. In the Felix films, as well as being adopted in Alice and Oswald, the question mark could "materialize" into a useful tool.

Felix Gets the Can (1925)

- Speech balloon

The speech balloon, a text device characteristic of comic strips, appears in silent cartoons quite frequently until the mid-1920s. The evolution in the use of balloons and texts in Felix's narrative throughout the 1920s deserves a study by itself, but in general (based on the films studied), we can observe that there is a tendency towards an increasingly smaller use of balloons.

Speech bubble like the one common in comics in *Felix Finds Out (1924)*

While Disney even uses some dialogue balloons in *Alice*, in *Oswald*, he chooses to use only the animation of texts and symbols, with rare occasions of balloons or intertitles (Merrit and Kaufman, 1993), with little or no text (only punctuation or symbols). The use of a balloon is observed to compose a gag, for example, when the character thinks or speaks, the balloon appears, and this becomes a gas balloon that will be useful for a given situation.

Oswald discovers a use for his balloon in *The Ocean Hop* (1927)

Balloon indicating the character's anger in *Felix the Cat: Politics* (1928)

Balloon indicating the moment of Julius's idea in *Alice's Balloon Race* (1926)

- Intertitle

The intertitle is a resource widely used in silent live-action cinema to convey the characters' speech lines. It can also be used to show the narrator's voice-over or indicate the passage of time.

In the films studied, intertitles are occasionally observed in *Alice* and *Felix*, while in *Oswald* the occurrence is rare, with the preference for more economical dialogue resources, such as pantomime or just one word or animated onomatopoeia without the balloon, as shown in the examples presented. In the film *Ocean Hop* (1927), intertitles appear only to indicate the passage of time.

Intertitle in *Ocean Hop* (1927)

Alice Gets Stung (1925)

Felix Hit the Deck (1927)

d) “Close-up” on sound source

Widely used in silent live action, this is a resource mentioned by Chion and Eisenstein (Manzano, 2003) that consists of a close-up shot of the supposed source² of a certain sound. The accompanying musician would possibly play the indicated sound, but even if the film is shown in silence, the viewer can imagine the sound. Just like in silent live-action films, this close-up is generally shown with a vignette (a shot with a round black mask on the edges, giving the viewer a spyglass image like).

Shot of bells indicating the call for enlistment in *Oswald - Great Guns* (1927)

Unlike live-action cinema, in silent cartoons, most of the time, this image is accompanied by an onomatopoeia of the corresponding sound. Although the information is redundant, in certain situations text animation can reinforce the sound characteristics of volume and timbre, as mentioned in the item "text and symbol animation".

e) Concert and dance

Even without control over the musical accompaniment, concert and dance numbers are frequent in Disney's silent films. According to authors Merrit & Kaufman, "Almost all the surviving silent Disneys make the representations of music a vital part of the humor and charm of the film". The authors also highlight the use of "musical forms to structure his silent narratives", which makes some films true "silent musicals" (1993, p. 20).

Like rhythmic establishing shots, musical scenes generally present a beat identified by repetition of movements or animation of musical notes. Animation of texts containing the onomatopoeia of animal sounds is also used when they were "touched", generally with a provocative action (or even mistreatment), for example by pulling their tail, squeezing their

² Even in a sound film, the concept of a sound source in an audiovisual work is always illusory, as the object shown in the image does not necessarily correspond exactly to the origin of the sound. Chion (1994) uses the concept of Audiovisual Contract to define the viewer's acceptance of the object that appears in the image as being the source of the sound.

belly or hammering their head. This type of gag with the "instrumentalization" of animals is also widely used at the beginning of the sound period in Disney films, but obviously without the need to use texts, as acoustic sounds could be added to the scene, contemplating what seemed to already be an old desire for a sound gag.

Insert shot revealing the animals inside the organ box in *Hungry Hobos* (1928)

In addition to the example already cited in *Alice Gets Stung* (1925) with the use of textual representation of animal sounds, musical notes are also used to convey the mood and rhythm of the music. The musician character's performance and the characters' dance also play a significant role in establishing the rhythm of the music to be used as accompaniment.

Animal Drums in *Alice Gets Stung* (1925)

Rat xylophone in *Rattled Alice by Rats* (1925)

Alice Rattled by Rats (1925)

In *Alice Gets Stung* (1925), there is a peculiar use of a scene to convey the "musical background" of a sad story that the victim-rabbit is about to tell to convince his hunter (Julius the cat) to spare his life. Insert shots show rabbits playing the violin and cello and in addition to the musical notes, flowers and hearts come out of the instruments to indicate the mood of the music.

Alice Gets Stung (1925)

These inserts can either serve as a reference for the accompanying music, or to compose the gag of a reference to the medium itself (a "Playing with the Medium" gag type, according to Wright (2012, p.94), in which the use of music evokes a certain emotion to help one character gain empathy for another. After the rabbit tells his story about having hungry cubs in his cave, the insert appears once again of the musical rabbits to conclude the story, which ends with the rabbit crying and Julius sensitized in tears.

We thus observe in Disney's work an anticipation of the importance of music in his animation creation process since the silent period. "Even before the advent of synchronized sound, Disney organized materials around both music and drama." Merrit & Kaufman (1993:20).

Gag with the goat organ grinder – in silent Oswald – *Rival Romeos* (1927) – then in sound *Mickey – Steamboat Willie* (1928).

It is noted that some of these visual devices are still used in the sound period, especially non-textual ones. Symbols such as musical notes, stars and some types of expression lines are still present in cartoon gags today. The gag that Oswald turns a goat into an organ after it eats sheet music in *Rival Romeos* (1927) is recycled in *Steamboat Willie* (1928), this time with control of the recorded sound accompaniment.

The use of balloons, texts and intertitles - whether to represent speech or noise - becomes completely unnecessary when synchronized sound is implemented, both in *Felix* and *Mickey*.

The legacy of the use of these devices partially lies in the differentiation of part of the visual language in the silent and sound periods. It is possible to see that, in the silent period, despite the possibility of sound accompaniment, the images must contain the entire narrative. By watching the films in silence, we were able to understand the whole story and follow the gags, as all the text information and sound representations were on the screen.

When we enter the sound period, we notice a significant difference in the role of sound in *Mickey* and *Felix*, although there is something in common: in both series, most representational devices are given away, especially those that could be replaced by speech. or sound effects³. According to Klein, "new visual gags were possible. Inanimate objects could

³ In the case of *Felix*, as stated only in unverified sources (i.e., Wikipedia filmography), there is a possibility that intertitles were removed for the re-release of the sound version of some silent films, which makes comparisons regarding the use of this specific device more difficult.

not only look alive, but they could also sound alive as well. (...) Felix could no longer turn a question mark into I skyhook with the same effect or tip his head or turn his tail into a suitcase. The graphic ideogram was replaced by Syncopation." (1993, p.11)

In the case of Disney's films from *Steamboat Willie* (1928) onwards, the soundtrack becomes a fundamental part of the film, as it contains not only an accompaniment, but vital information for understanding a narrative that has already been constructed carefully considering the sound part, with the development of a synchronization system. Disney's understanding of the importance of sound (especially music and sound effects) is easily observed in his creation process in *Steamboat Willie* and the result is not only the great change in the use of sound representation devices in relation to previously produced films *Plane Crazy* (1928) and *Gallopín Gaucho* (1928), but also a great interaction between what we see and hear. Crafton describes the impact of *Steamboat Willie*:

It was not the first sound cartoon (the Fleischers and Paul Terry had beaten Disney to this milestone), but it was the first one with singing, whistling, and audiovisual percussive effects (such as cats meowing when their tails were pulled) specifically designed for sync sound. After the film opened in November 1928, silent cartoon production was obsolete. The economics of sound film-making caused a realignment of the industry, with many independents and one major studio -- Sullivan's -- failing to make the change-over. (1996, p.134)

In the early years of sound *Mickey Mouse*, Disney maintained his preference for speech economy, with greater emphasis on the characters' action and expression, besides interaction with music. Due to his obsession with rhythm and synchrony, sound and image began to have an intrinsic relationship in his films. Not surprisingly, the effect achieved when the sound corresponds exactly to the movement of the image has become widely known as "mickey mousing" (Taberham, 2018, p.133). While music plays a role in driving emotion and rhythm (in addition to musical and dance performances), sound effects - often produced from musical instruments - highlight key actions and movements, accurately punctuating gags.

In Felix's first sound films there is also practically no dialogue. In *Woos Whoope* (1930) and *April Maze* (1930) it is noted that the narrative structure of the silent period is maintained, with only a few insertions of music and dance scenes, but it is not possible to observe a great symbiosis between sound and image, due to the fact of the sound being post-synchronized. According to Maltin (1987), producer Pat Sullivan's refusal to invest in the conversion to sound meant that in about a year Felix declined in popularity and became obsolete. For Klein:

Before sound, Felix lived in a fantasy world which was literally made-up of parts of speech and punctuation. After the introduction of sound, he became clumsy and sugary. Felix did not survive well after 1928. His graphic tricks lost more importance when they had to synchronize to clangs and thumps or harmonic strains. (1993, p.8)

Beyond the first phase of the sound period, there is still much to be explored regarding the influences and legacy of visual practices from the silent period on animation aesthetics, whether in relation to sound or image, or even dramatic and narrative issues. Taberham describes some of the major changes in the role of sound over time and how conventions bleed from one period to another (2018). Disney's musical films in the first sound period had an influence on the creation of Warner films (including Carl Stalling's own move to Warner in the early 1930s) which in turn, with a specific stylization and the establishment of a series of conventions in the use of sound effects (Wells, 1998), influenced an entire generation of cartoons.

Conclusion

As demonstrated, during the 1920s there was a consolidated language in US cartoon series, with visual codes established throughout the development of production techniques.

This study focused on a certain production context in which there was a tendency towards industrialization. It is important to highlight that in the same period animated films were produced using other techniques and styles. Crafton identifies productions in Europe and South America and mentions that "every country with a significant silent film industry also had a local animation industry" (1996, p.136). Other studies are necessary to identify the use of devices demonstrated in other techniques and locations. The biggest difficulty is finding copies of surviving films.

Manzano points out that silent cinema developed "its own grammar, full of resources that seek to make up for the absence of sound. The image composition becomes more complex, just as the articulation of images, juxtaposed by montage, seeks to create new meanings" (2003, p.46). However, with the advent of sound cinema, this grammar would have to adapt to the new reality of the synchronous reproduction capacity of sound. According to Maltin (1987), many of New York's animation filmmakers might have been content to release their silent films

with soundtracks and effects, as they did in 1929, but by 1930 there was no longer any doubt that making sound films was vital to the continued production of animation.

Cinema was forced to seek a new audiovisual relationship.

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Disclaimer: Ethnic, gender and racial stereotypes that were prevalent in the 1920s appear in the cited cartoons.